

QUIZ**LAST NAME: IJEH****FIRST NAME: LOWELL****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX (6)****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What is the major goal of an academic essay writing?

- The major goal of an academic essay is one that is focused in encouraging readers to accept popular ideas.
- The goal of an academic paper requires that, the idea should address the curiosity of all categories of readers that find the essay very interesting.
- An academic essay is aimed to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence.¹**
- Every academic essay writing is to strive and present materials that have not been written or published by any other author.

2. In-house jargons have grown to be a significant means of communication within an organization, yet it has incurred some level of setbacks that must be avoided, why should we avoid these setbacks?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Course pack: Period 4* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 2.

- It is because the use of jargons is not officially approved by the native speakers of English.
 - In-house jargon is not appropriate in documents addressing the general public such as leaflets or web pages.²**
 - Every visitor to an organization communicating with jargons are required to have some level of proficiency.
 - Jargons generally comes with codes that must be learnt among the users.
3. **In order to avoid plagiarism, every author is strongly advised to cite the source of where the information they are writing about come from, what is not true about plagiarism?**
- Plagiarism is wrong and unethical.
 - It is not fair to take peoples work and not giving them the desire credit.
 - It is a serious academic offense that can attract severe consequences.
 - It is a way of giving approval for the job of other authors.³**
4. **In EUCLID University, a credit is equivalent of International Credit Hour (ICH) which is the same with US credit system, what does International Credit Hour represent?**
- International credit hour represent the total aggregate of study hours a student participated in international courses.

² European Commission, *English Style Guide* (European Commission, 2011), 7.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 13.

- A credit hour represents the equivalent of 14 hours of lecturing (with associated assignments) over the course of a semester which is 14 or 15 weeks.⁴**
 - International credit system that run for a semester for the period of 17 or 18 weeks.
 - This represent a complete semester activities without associated assignments.
5. **What is the prime consideration when using abbreviations in an essay writing?**
- Abbreviation should account for speedy essay writing and also help researchers to save more space.
 - Readers may find abbreviation useful because it propel them to do more researches on unfamiliar words.
 - They should be very familiar and easily understood to most readers.⁵**
 - Abbreviations sometimes shield young authors from making common mistake in the process of writing out the affected words fully.
6. **Drafted Legislation is a stage in the legislation process in the EU in other word, it is used to qualify Commission acts, what is a Draft legislation?**
- The volume of legislative act that have completed the approval process.
 - It is the approved, and ready to go writing constitution in the EU commission.

4. Cleenewerck and Gulma, 1-2.

5. European Commission. *English Style Guide*. (European Commission, 2020), 22.

- In relation to EU legislation process, a drafted Legislation is a stage where all unapproved laws are rejected.
 - The word draft denotes that the act in question has not yet been formally approved by the Commission.**⁶
7. **An academic essay is aimed to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence, what is not true about a good essay?**
- An academic essay should answer a question or task that must be approved by all readers.**⁷
 - It should have a thesis statement, answer to the question as well as an argument.
 - It should try to present or discuss subject to develop a thesis via a set of closely related points by reasoning and evidence.
 - An academic essay should include relevant examples, supporting evidence and information from academic texts or credible sources.
8. **What is primary regulations as clarified by the European Union?**
- Primary regulations explain the intention and motives of the law making organs in the EU.
 - The way in which the European Union operates is regulated by a series of Treaties and various other agreements having similar status.**⁸
 - These are the imputes originating from member countries in the EU that represent the wish of their citizens.

6. EU Commission, 52.

7. Turabian, 2.

8. European Commission 52.

9. Turabian, 22.

- The first set of Laws that spell out procedures on how the EU would be governed by the member states.
9. **In writing an academic paper, it does not look very good to have too many quotes, so you will need to paraphrase at times, which of these statements is *not* correct about paraphrasing?**
- Paraphrasing means you cannot just change a couple of words and rearrange the sentence structure.
- The exact sentence you used to express the author's ideas must be different from the style the author used.
- The information that you are providing must be an accurate representation of what the author originally wrote.
- It must be your words only, the language you use cannot resemble the author's works.⁹**
10. **What is the major difference between Major Paper (MP) and the Response Paper (RP)?**
- There is virtually no difference between both of them.
- According to Euclid University Authority, major papers are writing by PHD students, while response are the products master degree students.
- Major Paper are quite different from response papers, notably because they are meant to be very academic and therefore impersonal, whereas response papers are by nature more interactive and therefore conversational.¹⁰**
- Every information on the major papers are given by the student supervisors, while that of response paper are supplied by the student themselves.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 6.

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